

EARTHQUAKE AND TSUNAMI EVENTS FROM THE EYES OF WITNESSES: EXTRACTING DESCRIPTIONS OF GEOLOGIC PHENOMENA FROM NARRATIVES ANALYSIS

Ma. Mylene Martinez-Villegas, Renato U. Solidum, Jr., Lucille Rose D. Sanico, Charmaine V. Villamil, Jeffrey S. Perez, Ruben C. Lamela, Melcario D. Pagtalunan and Florenette B. Garcia

ABSTRACT: This study focuses on significant earthquake and tsunami events that occurred more than 20 years ago and up to the present. The aim is to have a better understanding of people's experiences and how individuals describe and put life to what they have observed. For this study we used qualitative approach through review of narrative interviews that were video documented. These resource persons who have vivid descriptions about experienced earthquake and/or tsunami events were asked to narrate what they can recall. These video-documented interviews are valuable records of descriptions of geologic phenomena that may have helped shape perceptions and understanding as these may influence future decision-making in terms of actions to take in case of similar events. The interviews were transcribed and descriptions of earthquake- and tsunami-related phenomena were extracted. These include descriptions of events such as ground shaking, ground rupture, liquefaction, and natural signs of incoming tsunami (water recedes, rumbling sound) as seen, heard and felt by witnesses during actual event. The 1976 Moro Gulf, 1994 Oriental Mindoro and the 1990 Luzon earthquakes among others are just some of the past events specifically Negros Oriental and Bohol 2013 earthquakes were also included.

KEYWORDS: earthquake; tsunami; narratives; eyewitnesses; geologic phenomena

1. INTRODUCTION

Stories of experiences that people tell are valuable sources of first-hand information specially for major geologic events. This paper presents how ordinary people describe geological processes or phenomena as they saw it, heard it and felt it, in the context of their understanding. Descriptions of ground shaking, ground rupture, liquefaction, and actual tsunami as they were experienced are the focus of this paper.

Our interest in this paper differs because we focus on descriptive narratives concerning experiences of people who have directly witnessed these major events. Most interviewees are residents and officials in the local community. The importance of their perspective lies in its use when applied to earthquake and tsunami awareness and preparedness in the Philippines. At least seven (7) significant recent historical earthquake and tsunami events were identified and sampled for this study. These include: 1973 Ragay Gulf Earthquake, 1976 Moro Gulf Earthquake and Tsunami, 1990 Luzon Earthquake, 1990 Antique Earthquake, 1994 Mindoro Earthquake and Tsunami, 2012 Negros Oriental Earthquake and 2013 Bohol Earthquake.

2. METHODS

This work is a product of review of archived interviews that have accumulated through the years starting the 1990s. The study aimed to recapture original descriptions from the video-documented interviews of people during major events. Most interviews relied on recollection of people about these specific events. For the 1990 Luzon event, files of the video-documented interviews taken in 1993 were retrieved from the PHIVOLCS archive. Additional interviews were gathered in 2010 for the 20th year commemoration of the 1990 Luzon Earthquake. For the 1976 Moro Gulf and 1994 Mindoro Oriental events, the interviews were part of the 2006 project for tsunami risk mitigation wherein a component of the project is to video-document interviews of survivors and eyewitnesses. For the more recent earthquakes such as Negros in 2012 and Bohol in 2013, the interviews took place a few days to a few weeks immediately after the event. A total of 13 interviews were used. These interviews were reviewed, transcribed and then analyzed. Common themes of descriptions about observations relatable to known geologic phenomena were mined out manually. The excerpts were extracted, quoted and used in this paper.

This paper, with its emphasis on eyewitnesses as respondents, is qualitative in nature. Its significance lies in the story-telling – the sharing of a wealth of narratives – full of the descriptions and insights of people having firsthand experience and whose narratives can be used to further understand the people's views and the event.

3. SOME SIGNIFICANT EARTHQUAKE EVENTS EXAMINED

For this paper, major earthquake events reviewed include the 1976 Moro Gulf Earthquake, 16 July 1990 Earthquake, 15 November 1994 Mindoro Earthquake, 2012 Negros Oriental Earthquake, 2013 Bohol Earthquake, and additional contributions from the 1973 Ragay Gulf, 14 June 1990 Antique. Details of these events are presented in Table 1.

The interviews were reviewed to look for descriptions of ground shaking, ground rupture, liquefaction, and tsunami. Based on PHIVOLCS (2015) flyer on earthquake and earthquake hazards, the following are the technical explanation or definition of the earthquake-related phenomena whose descriptions we wanted to extract from the archived interviews.

Ground shaking refers to the disruptive up and down and sideways motion (vibration) experienced during an earthquake.

Ground rupture is the deformation on the ground that marks the intersection of the fault with the earth's surface.

Liquefaction is a phenomenon wherein sediments, especially near bodies of water, behave like liquid similar to a quick sand.

Tsunami is a series of waves caused commonly by an earthquake under the sea

Table 1. Details of Earthquakes included in this study

	<i>Event</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Local Time</i>	<i>Magnitude/Depth</i>	<i>Remarks (Impacts,# casualties etc)</i>
1	1973 Ragay Gulf Earthquake	17 March 1973	4:37 pm	M 7.0/ 33 km	14 casualties Horizontal displacement of 1.1-3.4 meters;
2	1976 Moro Gulf Earthquake and Tsunami	17 August 1976	12:11 am	M 8.1/ 33 km	Estimated height up to 9 m, Waves reported to have inundated as far as 75 m to 200 m to as far as 1 km inland; reports of estimated deaths between 4000-8000+
3	1990 Antique Earthquake	14 June 1990	7:40am	M7.1/ 15 km	Killed 8 people, Town of Culasi most affected/ hardest hit; building suffered minor to severe damages
4	1990 Luzon Earthquake	16 July 1990	4:26 pm	M 7.8/ 25 km	1,621 reported casualties; rupture length: at least 120 km horizontal displacement: maximum of 6.1 m; widespread liquefaction in Pangasinan and La Union
5	1994 Mindoro Earthquake and Tsunami	15 November 1994	3:15 am	M 7.1 / 7-12 km	78 casualties, tsunami with heights between 2-4 meter and inundation areas 13-250 meters affected the coastal communities of Calapan, Baco, Puerto Galera, San Teodoro; rupture length: about 35 km
6	2012 Negros Oriental Earthquake	6 February 2012	11:49 am	M 6.9 / 5-10 km	Local tsunami 4-5 m high, affected coastal areas of Negros Oriental uplift <1m.
7	2013 Bohol Earthquake	15 October 2013	8:12 am	M 7.2/ 12 km	200 deaths, 6 km surface rupture, 2.5 m vertical displacement, 600 affected families.

Sources: Badillo and Astilla, 1978; Punongbayan and others, 1992; PHIVOLCS, 1994; PHIVOLCS, 2015; PHIVOLCS 2013; Bautista and others, 2012; Morante, 1976; Manahan and Lasala, 1998; PHIVOLCS Earthquake Catalog

4. COMPILATION OF NARRATIVES FROM INTERVIEWS

What is intended in this work is to recapture original descriptions as narrated. In the descriptive narrative approach taken by this work, we looked at how people remembered the event and how these were narrated just as these happened. To arrive at a narrative form, all selected video-recorded interviews retrieved from the archive were transcribed and analyzed qualitatively based on selected identified categories- for this case – ground rupture, ground shaking, liquefaction, and tsunami. This thematic analysis emphasized on

mining out what were said (Riessman, 2004), from which portions were selected for presentation and discussion.

The narrative inquiry is the study of human experience involving the retelling of stories (Clandinin and Huber, 2014) using interviews as a data collection tool (Connelly and Clandinin, 1990). Narratives are stories people tell about their lives (Gray, Fergus, and Fitch, 2005). – in this case, an earthquake related event – that were familiar as these were experienced by the narrators themselves. Here we see the importance of the “point of view” that distinguishes narratives from stories (Frid, Ohlen, and Bergbom, 2000). These narratives are interesting because they are situated within a broader cultural and social context and thus reveal social structures and processes. A particular strength of the narrative approach is that it enables us to analyze how human beings typically understand and represent their own lives.

Observations about the event based on interviews with eyewitnesses occasionally would appear in typical technical reports on earthquakes and tsunami (Morante, 1974; Nakata, 1996; Badillo, 1978; Tsutsumi and others, 2015). However, most often, the essence of the local language description is lost not only in the translation but into the more technical aspect or the report writing style. For example, the 1990 Luzon Earthquake had very detailed documentation of ground rupture. There were witnesses of the actual rupture event, and one is described below:

“Marvin Garde (17), a high school student, was in the paddy field couple of meters off the fault rupture. He first heard rumbling sound followed by mild shaking that lasted about 5 seconds, and then felt severe quake for about 10 seconds. He observed the lateral displacement 2 seconds later the severe quake had started. The displacement was accompanied with another rumbling sound lasted for a second and followed by the vertical displacement that lasted for 5 seconds to be completed.” – from Nakata and others, 1996

Vivid first-hand descriptions may be lost when data is translated and incorporated into a typical technical report. In this work, we opted to recapture the descriptions to retain the original local language as transcribed. This enables us to see how the event was originally described in local language so as not to lose the idea or thought.

In this work, we intend to share the event as seen, felt or heard, and remembered then described by people of no science background. These actual descriptions can be used as guide for geologists and social scientists to have a sense of how people with no science background describe certain phenomena in the language that is more understandable to most people- in the common language they are familiar with. This kind of method was used and is being pursued by Martinez-Villegas and others (2015) for the Japan March 2011 Earthquake and Tsunami and in earlier works of Martinez-Villegas and others (2010a and 2010b).

4.1 Actual Descriptions of earthquake-related phenomena

The following are excerpts from narratives are descriptions about the experienced earthquake and tsunami event, and focuses on what witnesses felt, saw, heard as the earthquake or tsunami struck, and what actions they took. The summary of descriptions is presented in Table 2.

4.1.1 Ground Rupture

Of all the phenomena associated with an earthquake event, witnessing the surface rupturing of the ground is probably the most interesting. We are fortunate to be able to capture descriptions from several eyewitnesses. During the 1973 Ragay Gulf earthquake, a witness (ARF-RG1973) describes seeing “nag-crack ang lupa tapos bumagsak ng halos isang metro” or that the ground cracked and one part “fell a meter lower”. One witness (MG-LE1990) of the Luzon 1990 earthquake describes seeing “bumibitak ng malalaki..nakataaas yung kalahati, yung kalahati nakababa..” that there were huge cracks then one part of the ground rose, while the other went down. A more recent description we captured came from the eyewitness from 2013 Bohol earthquake (MP-BE2013) who described seeing the actual rupture narrating that when she went out, the ground was still level, until she heard a loud sound she described as “boog, boog” accompanying the moment of rupture, when she saw the land rise up before her eyes.

4.1.2 Ground Shaking

One of the most commonly felt and described is the shaking of the ground. The ground motion of the shaking as “up-down” and “sideways” during an earthquake can be discerned from the narratives. In most interviews, people tend to describe the motion with words- “paganito”, “paganyan”, “paganon” which can be translated to “like this” or “towards this (direction)” accompanied by hand gestures showing up-down or sideways motion. There were some who actually had more imaginative way of describing. What is interesting is how people have varied ways of describing this. In one interview (PS-ME1994), the up-down motion was likened to “parang itinahip” referring to the up-down motion one does with the “bilao” (woven flat basket for shaking and cleaning rice) while shaking the grains to remove husks when cleaning the rice. The eyewitness is a barangay official whose source of livelihood and background is farming.

During the 16 July 1990, a survivor (PD-LE1990) from the collapsed Hyatt Hotel described the motion as “parang idrinibol” or dribbled like a ball, suggesting dominant up-down motion or movement. In another interview, again from the 1990 Luzon Earthquake, the eyewitness (MG-LE1990) also working in the field at the time of the event, and really close to the epicenter of the 16 July 1990 earthquake, gave the vivid description of that ground that is “umaalon” or “papa-alon” or wave-like referring to the surface waves as seen and felt manifested by the ground movement. One witness (SR-LE1990) recalled hearing “uungot-ungot” or “creaking sound” while trapped under the debris of the collapsed Nevada Hotel, which accompanied the aftershocks.

4.1.3 Tsunami

For a tsunami event, there are three (3) significant natural signs: the actual shaking, the water recedes and the rumbling sound that follows when the seawater comes rushing back. Although not all the 3 signs are always observed, it is noteworthy to see how these were described by people living by the shore. For the 1976 Moro Gulf earthquake, the description by a survivor (CN-MG1976) includes hearing loud rumbling sound “kusog kaayo na dagook” as narrated in Cebuano. He also describes seeing houses being plowed, that he saw the houses coming towards them like trucks running at a high speed. During the November 1994 Mindoro event, a resident (AB-ME1994) described as seeing the sea retreat with “Sa dagat ay kita ko’y, malaki ang kati. Malayo ang tubig..” and hearing “ugong” - roaring, howling noise from the sea. “Kati” is a very local Tagalog word used to refer to “low tide” or “ebb” commonly used in the coastal fishing communities in the Southern Tagalog region area- for this case in Mindoro Oriental.

4.1.4 Liquefaction

Several descriptions for liquefaction were also noted. A witness of the 1990 Antique Earthquake (JB-AE1990) describes seeing the ground break where water mixed with mud gushed out about 3 meters high – “kita ko yung lupa bumitak...sumingaw yung tubig mga 3 metro yung taas ng tubig..putik, itim ba.” During the Mindoro 1994 Earthquake a witness (ET-ME1994) describes feeling the warm water spurting from the ground or “nagpupuslitan ang tubig na maninit galing sa lupa...” A witness during the Moro Gulf earthquake of 1976 describes seeing cracks on the ground and saw smoke coming out where in its original Cebuano wordings- “nag sige mi ug tapak atong yuta nga nagliki..dani nag-aso ang yuta miliki among gitabonan..”

Table 2. Some examples of descriptions that were extracted from the interviews

		<i>Translation</i>	<i>From</i>
<i>I</i>	<i>GROUND RUPTURE</i>		
1.1	"Tapos doon lang talaga. Kasi balak ko doon tumakbo kasi bakante yan e. Yung yung banda roon lang yan dito sa baba yun tumaas...Oo ganyan na talaga. Umangat na yun banda doon...Oo nakita ko talaga sir (yung pag-angat)..Noong paglabas ko lebel pa, tapos yun nga, boog-boog-boog yung ganoon paglabas ko talaga yung pag-isang putok na malakas yun biglang umangat. Yun talaga ang nakita ko"	"I planned to run there because it was open space. That lower part there (of that area) had risen. I really saw it myself, sir. When I first went out, the ground was all level. Then the noise came: boog, boog, boog!! We heard a single loud bang and the land rose. I really saw that."	MP-BE2013
1.2	"Nag crack ang lupa tapos bumagsak ng halos isang metro, "napansin din namin na nasira yung bakod namin tapos may bitak sa lupa"	"The ground cracked and fell almost a meter lower than its usual height. We noticed that our fence broke and there were cracks on the ground."	ARF-RG1973
1.3	"Noong una kalabog. Kalabog sa ilalim ng lupa. Dahan-dahang yumanig. Pagkatapos ulit di nagtagal umuga na naman ulit. Yung papa-alon alon ng ganyan (hand gestures- wave). Sa bukid 'yung mga lupa uma-alon alon na. Umugang ganyan (hand gestures). Malakas 'yung uga talagang malakas. Oo malakas.	"First we heard the crashing sound down from underneath. The ground shook slowly. It didn't take long before it shook again, this time in waves (gesturing with the hand). Out in the fields, the land was riding out in waves (gesturing again). Yes, there was very, very strong ground shaking. There was a loud	MG-LE1990

	<p>Talagang umuugong akala mo buhawing kuwan umu-ugong. Talagang bumibitak 'yung lupa. Papaliit lang, una maliit lang 'yung bitak. Malakas na uga oo. Malakas na malakas. Pagkatapos bumitak 'yung lupa. Yumayanig, Noong gumaganoon 'yung lupa pagkatapos umaalon ng ganyan. Umaalon ng ganyan. (hand gestures- like wave) Pagtapos nag-bibitak ng ganyan tapos 'yung bumibitak ng malalaki.... Ganoon 'yun. Tapos eh hindi naman nagtagal tumaas naman 'yung isa ganoon na lang. Nakataas na ngayon 'yung ano 'yung kalahati. 'Yung kalahati nakababa. Nandoon ako sa mababa. Nakita bumibitak. Malalaking bitak. “</p>	<p>rambling noise, like a tornado. The ground was really breaking, small at first." "It was a strong tremor, very, very strong. Then the ground cracks appeared. The ground was shaking. Then the ground went this way and that, in waves (hand gestures a wave-like motion). The breaks in the ground got bigger. It wasn't long before one part of the ground rose higher than the other half, just like that. I was at the lower part of it, seeing the very big cracks happen."</p>	
2	<i>GROUND SHAKING</i>		
2.1	“...tapos biglang gumalaw...mabilis, mabilis, parang ambilis.Hindi mo alam, parang lumulundag yung lupa.”	“...then it suddenly moved, it was very fast, so fast. You don't know, it was like the ground looked like it was jumping..”	LL-LE1990
2.2	“Yung initial movement, ganon, parang sideways, later on up and down, up and down yun walang tigil.. tapos maya-maya, uungot ungot..”	“The initial movement was sideways, later on, up and down, up and down nonstop. Then this was followed by this creaking sound...”	SR-LE1990
2.3	“..lumindol na..una hindi pa masyado malakas, napatayo na kami lahat, pangalawang bugso yung pinakamalakas na, parang nagdribol na ng bola, parang ganun..tapos hindi na kami nakatakbo..pagtakbo namin dun sa second na pintuan yun na yung nag stop kami lahat dun, pagtingin sa itaas, andyan na yung Hyatt, nagigiba na.”	"The it shook. At first it wasn't that strong. We were all prompted to stand up. The second shaking was the strongest, like the dribbling of a ball. We couldn't run. When we could, we ran, and we all stopped at that second door. When we looked up, there we saw Hyatt (hotel) starting to crumble."	PD-LE1990
2.4	“...Nagising kami dahil umuga ng medyo malakas, umuga ng umuga tapos biglang para kaming itinahip sa bilao, tinahip kami...pagnakatatlong ganun (hand movement showing sideways motion) biglang itinahip na parang pataas baba, mabilis.”	“..We were awakened because it shook, it was a little strong, then it shook and shook again, like we were being winnowed from a woven basket ...after thrice moving sideways, we were like being winnowed from a woven basket and moved up-down, it was very quick..”	PS-ME1994
3	<i>TSUNAMI</i>		
3.1	“...Sa dagat ay kita ko'y, malaki ang kati. Malayo ang tubig, Pero...ugong yang laot na yan..E yung ugong na yan, sabi ko, ako'y tatakbo...tatakbo paparito, kako'y lumabas kayo..may tubig, alon..e di nagtatakbo na kami”	"I saw that the water ebbed low and far into the sea. But the howling of the water was very loud. With that I told myself to run close here (to land). I called out, 'Come out and run! There are huge waves coming,' And so we all ran hard."	AB-ME1994
3.2	“Nung nag lindol e di kami'y nag akap-akap na, hindi kami bumangon sa sobrang lakas ng lindol..tapos nung matapos ang lindol, biglang sinabayan, sumunod ng malakas na ugong...”	"While it was shaking, we all held onto each other. We couldn't get up from the force of the shaking. Then when it was done, there followed a loud rambling noise...”	ET-ME1994
3.3	“..Madilim na nga, at malakas naa.. Yung lagaslas ng tubig, nga sigawan ang mga tao "May tubig! May tubig!" siguro mga seconds laang yun aaa at magkapanunod na yung lindol at saka yun malakas na lagaslas ng tubig..”	"..It was dark already, and it was strong. With the sound of rippling of waters, the people shouted, 'Water! There's water! In just seconds, the earthquake and the strong gushing of water came in succession."	MD-ME1994
3.4	“Paggawas namo sa kalsada, nakadungog mi	“When we reached the road we heard a loud	CN-MG1976

	<p>og kusog kaayo nga dagook nga wala mi kasabot kung tubig ba o dalug-dug o unsa. Wala jud mi kasabot! Nidagan mi paingon dinhi aron makagawas mi. Pagdagan namo, gitagbo man pod mi sa tubig nga naay dala na mga balay nga nanglutaw na. Posible man molutaw nang mga kabalayan sa baybayon (coastal areas) kay gipatong ra man ug bato. Nanglutaw na ang mga gianod na panimalay unya kusog kayo ang ligid ba. Mura anang mga dagkong sakyanan bitaw kung kusog ang padagan. Ingon ana, dayon ang among nabati ato sir, ingon ana na, gianod mi sa tubig nga perting kusoga. Nabulag ming magtiayon, nabuhian namo ang among mga bata. Dayon diri nako gidala o, sa center gyud tungod.”</p>	<p>rumbling sound. We did not understand what the cause of that sound was, was it because of water or thunder or something else. We did not understand! We ran here to escape the cause of the sound. But as we were running, we saw the water coming towards us and it was carrying floating houses with it. It is possible for those houses along the coastal areas to float because they were only built on top of the rocks. The houses were floating and rolling rapidly. It was coming towards us like trucks running at great speed. Then the strong waves separated us and we both lost our children. I found myself washed aground near the Center.”</p>	
4	<i>LIQUEFACTION</i>		
4.1	<p>“Naramdaman ko ang lindol, parang paganon, mabilis. Duon ako sa palayan, tapos naramdaman ko, kita ko yung lupa, bumitak tapos magbitak, sumingaw yung tubig mga 3 meters yung taas ng tubig..putik, itim ba, itim na putik..malambot na lupa, mayroong crack”</p>	<p>"I felt the shaking going this way (gesture), it was fast. I was out there on the rice field, then I felt and saw the ground break. After that, water gushed and spewed from the ground about 3 meters up in the air. It was mud -- black mud, soft soil. There were cracks.</p>	JB-AE1990
4.2	<p style="text-align: center;">Original in Cebuano</p> <p>“Mao na nga pagnaog namo, nag sige mi ug tapak atong yuta nga nagliki. Miliki man ang yuta tungod sa linog. Dani nag-aso ang yuta miliki among gitabonan unya ang akong magulang nga gikan sa nilaag kay kining ulitawo laagan man kung magabii pwerteng katawa kay ingon siya”</p>	<p>"When we came down outside, we kept on stepping on the cracks. There were cracks on the ground due to the earthquake. We saw smoke coming out of the cracks.."</p>	HD-MG1976
4.3	<p>"..Naramdaman ko nagpupuslitan ang tubig na mainit galing sa lupa, sa ilalim.."</p>	<p>“I felt the warm water spurting from the ground..from underneath”</p>	ET-ME1994

5. CONCLUSION

There is a wealth of information that can be extracted in interviews with people who witnessed earthquake events. What were presented in this paper are just some examples of descriptions under review. The plan is to compile useful common and not so common descriptions used by ordinary people to narrate these geological phenomena. What is significant is when a phenomenon is likened to what people can relate to in everyday life. These are useful guide for scientists not only in documenting events but also a good tool in trying to understand how people relate to these events. Describing specific geologic events is an expression of how people make sense of their own experience. To better understand a particular phenomenon, these interviews need to be further reviewed. These creative descriptions can potentially be used in information, education and communication materials.

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ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Ma. Mylene Martinez-Villegas is a geologist and Chief Science Research Specialist (Chief SRS) of the Geologic Disaster Awareness and Preparedness Division (GDAPD) of the Philippine Institute of Volcanology and Seismology (PHIVOLCS-DOST). She holds a MS Geology from Arizona State University (USA) and M Development Communication from University of the Philippines -Open University (UPOU). She received her BS Geology from the University of the Philippines, Diliman. She is currently working on her Doctor of Communication at UPOU. She may be contacted through her email: mylene.villegas@phivolcs.dost.gov.ph

Renato U. Solidum, Jr. is the Director of PHIVOLCS. He received his PhD from Scripps Institute of Oceanography, University of California, San Diego, MS in Geology from University of Illinois, Chicago and BS Geology from the University of the Philippines-Diliman.

Jeffrey Perez is a geologist and is currently Supervising Science Research Specialist and Section head of the Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) R&D of GDAPD. He received his BS Geology from UP-Diliman and MS Civil and Environmental Engineering from Saitama University, Japan. He joined PHIVOLCS in 1999.

Lucille Sanico is Science Research Specialist II (SRSII) in the Materials Development Section (MDS) of GDAPD. She is a graduate of BS Industrial Education from Technological University of the Philippines. She joined PHIVOLCS in 2007. She is involved in development of information materials and capacity building program of the institute.

Charmaine Villamil is SRS II at PHIVOLCS and is a graduate of geology from UP Diliman. She joined PHIVOLCS in 2005. She is a member of the DRR R&D Section of GDAPD and is involved in capacity building activities of the institute and studies of earthquake risk perception.

Florenette Garcia is SRS II, and is a Civil Engineer. She is a graduate of Andres Bonifacio College, Dipolog City. She joined PHIVOLCS in 1995 and is based in the PHIVOLCS Seismic Station in Dipolog City.

Ruben Lamela is SR Assistant and joined PHIVOLCS in 1988. He is a member of the Materials Development Section (MDS) under the GDAPD of PHIVOLCS and is involved in the documentation by photo and video of significant events.

Melcario Pagtalunan is Senior SRS and is a Mechanical Engineer. He joined PHIVOLCS in 1990. He is currently the section head of the MDS-GDAPD and is responsible for the programming and development of different information materials specifically development of print, video and exhibit materials for information, education and communication. His group is also in-charge of phot-video documentation of significant events.

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